

Exploring the Functions of Glycomes with Glycan Microarrays

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The interactions of glycans with their binding partners, governed by an intricate 'glyco-code', influence many of the key biological processes in all living organisms. As prominent host cell surface molecules, glycans mediate cell adhesion and trigger cell signalling, and serve as attachment sites for microbes playing a critical role in colonization and infection. Glycan microarray technologies, first introduced in 2002 by Professor Ten Feizi and colleagues at Imperial College London (ICL), have revolutionized approaches to the molecular dissection of glycan-protein interactions and gained significant momentum worldwide. The ICL Carbohydrate Microarray Facility, since its foundation in 2012, has become an internationally leading operation, enabling collaborative studies on diverse glycan-mediated interactions involving the broad biomedical community (<https://www.imperial.ac.uk/glycosciences/carbohydrate-microarray-facility/>). I will highlight the unique resource we possess within our Facility, our recent contributions to unraveling glycan-mediated interactions at the host-microbe interface, and the latest advances in generating glycome-scale microarrays.

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